

Comparative Study on Analysis & Design of Skew Bridge by STAAD and ETABS Software using Finite Element Method

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ABSTRACT

Skew bridges are required to cross the drains at any angle other than normal. These can be helpful in making straight crossing or utilizing the available land where normal crossing are either impossible or not suitable. The slab bridges are uneconomical for large spans due to excessive design thickness but good for small spans due to its easy execution.

Bending Moment result comparison between both software i.e. Staad Pro & Etabs show little variation: For Span 15 m on Staad Pro & Etabs is 74.518 kn/sq.mm & 68.40kn/sq.mm respectively, For Span 17 m on Staad Pro & Etabs is 71.47 kn/sq.mm & 66.70 kn/sq.mm respectively & For Span 19 m on Staad Pro & Etabs is 79.73 kn/sq.mm & 71.95 kn/sq.mm respectively. At constant skew angle for varying span length the torsional bending moment gradually shift toward obtuse/acute angle. In both the software i.e. STAAD and ETAB the ETAB give more appropriate result in compare to STAAD.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Bridge is an important structure required for the transportation network. Now a day with the fast innovation in technology the conventional bridges have been replaced by the cost effective structured system. For analysis and design of these bridges the most efficient methods are available. Different methods which can be used for analysis and design are AASHTO, Finite element method, Grillage and Finite strip method.

OBJECTIVES

- Study of Skew Bridge with different length under Loading Condition.

METHODOLOGY

Skew bridges are required to cross the drains at any angle other than normal. These can be helpful in making straight

crossing or utilizing the available land where normal crossing are either impossible or not suitable, depending on the length of short diagonal of skew slab being less or greater than its span measured along the traffic. Two specimens tested experimentally, i.e.

1. Skew slab with ratio of short diagonal to span less than unity.
2. Skew slab with ratio of short diagonal to span greater than unity.

ANALYSIS & RESULTS

STAAD PRO

Following steps are required in a sequence for proper completion:

Step-1 Preparation of geometry of tower in STAAD PRO

Fig 4.1 Plan view of slab with 15m span length at 15° skew angle

Fig 4.2 3D view of slab with 15m span length at 15° skew angle

Fig 4.3 Plan view of slab with 17m span length at 15° skew angle

Fig 4.4 3D view of slab with 17m span length at 15° skew Angle

Fig 4.5 Plan view of slab with 19m span length at 15° skew angle

Fig 4.6 3D view of slab with 19m span length at 15° skew angle
Step-2 Assigning of support conditions.

Fig 4.7 Support on slab with 15m span length at 15° skew angle

Fig 4.8 Support on slab with 17m span length at 15° skew angle

Fig 4.9 Support on slab with 19m span length at 15° skew angle

Step-3 Assigning vehicle load as per specification.

Fig 4.10 Load on slab with 15m span length at 15° skew angle

Fig 4.11 Load on slab with 17m span length at 15° skew angle

Fig 4.12 Load on slab with 19m span length at 15° skew angle

Step-4 Analysis

Fig 4.13 Analysis of slab with 15m span length at 15° skew angle

Fig 4.14 Analysis of slab with 17m span length at 15° skew angle

Fig 4.15 Analysis of slab with 19m span length at 15° skew angle

**GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION MOMENT ON BRIDGE BY BOTH SOFTWARE
GRAPH OF MAXIMUM DISPLACEMENT**

Graph 5.1 Maximum Displacement Graph

GRAPH OF MAXIMUM STRESS

Graph 5.2 Maximum Stress Qx Graph

Graph 5.3 Maximum Stress Qy Graph

CONCLUSION

The load capacity of the tilting slab increases as the tilting angle increases. Up to the angle of inclination 15° the behavior of the slanted slab is almost similar to the rectangular slab.

1. Considerable torsion of deck slab.
2. Displacement result comparison between both software i.e. Staad Pro & Etabs show very nominal variation:
 - a. For Span 15 m on Staad Pro & Etabs is 17.016mm & 17.047mm respectively.
 - b. For Span 17 m on Staad Pro & Etabs is 14.641mm & 14.204mm respectively.
 - c. For Span 19 m on Staad Pro & Etabs is 13.638mm & 13.218mm respectively.
3. Bending Moment result comparison between both software i.e. Staad Pro & Etabs show little variation:
 - a. For Span 15 m on Staad Pro & Etabs is 74.518 kn/sq.mm & 68.40 kn/sq.mm respectively.
 - b. For Span 17 m on Staad Pro & Etabs is 71.47 kn/sq.mm & 66.70 kn/sq.mm respectively.
 - c. For Span 19 m on Staad Pro & Etabs is 79.73 kn/sq.mm & 71.95 kn/sq.mm respectively.
4. At constant skew angle for varying span length the torsional bending moment gradually shift toward obtuse/acute angle.

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